

ECONOSCITECH INTEGRATION

ISSUE
6

INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC
ELECTRONIC JOURNAL

TASHKENT STATE
UNIVERSITY OF ECONOMICS

American University
of Technology

Powered by Arizona State University®

ISSN: 3060-5075

Acceptance of articles
PUBLISHED MONTHLY

ARTICLE CONTRIBUTORS
PROFESSORS, SCHOLARS,
SPECIALISTS, AND RESEARCHERS

Google
Scholar

Academic
Resource
Index
ResearchBib

BASE

OpenAIRE

doi
Digital
Object
Identifier

OPEN ACCESS

CONTACT:

+998 94 3540880

<https://econoscitech-integration-journal.uz>

2026

EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Zufarova Nozima Gulamiddinovna
DSc., Dean of Tourism Faculty, TSUE

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Makhmudov Nosir Makhmudovich
DSc., Prof., Academician

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Suyunov Dilmurod Xolmurodovich
Doctor of Economics (DSc), Professor,

DEPUTY EDITOR-IN-CHIEF:

Allayarov Shamsiddin Amanullayevich
doctor of economics (DSC), professor

RESPONSIBLE SECRETARY:

Otaboyev Axmed Maxsudbek o'g'li
TSUE independent researcher

THE SCIENTIFIC-POPULAR
ELECTRONIC JOURNAL
"ECONOSCITECH-INTEGRATION"
HAS BEEN REGISTERED UNDER
THE NUMBER C-5669651 BY THE
AGENCY FOR INFORMATION AND
MASS COMMUNICATIONS (AOKA)
OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN,
EFFECTIVE FROM OCTOBER 9, 2024.

In accordance with Resolution No. 384/6 dated April 10, 2026, issued by the Presidium of the Supreme Attestation Commission under the Ministry of Higher Education, Science and Innovation of the Republic of Uzbekistan, this journal is included in the list of recommended international scientific publications for publishing the primary research findings of doctoral dissertations in the field of Economic Sciences.

Partners: Tashkent State University of Economics / American University of Technology in Tashkent (AUT)

Electronic publication, Issue 6. 374 pages.
Approved for publication on Iyun, 2026.

Editorial Board Members:

Sharipov Kongratbay Avezimbetovich,
Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor

Teshabayev To'liqin Zakirovich,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Said Irandoust,
Doctor of Chemical Engineering Sciences,
Professor

Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich,
Doctor of Economics, (DSc), Professor

Tokunaga Masahiro,
professor, PhD of Economics of the Faculty of
Business and Commerce

Debasis Das,
professor Department of Computer Science

Nitin Goje,
professor and Program Lead - Computer Science

Nargizakhon Shamshieva
Doctor of Economic Sciences, Professor

Rakhmonov Norim Razzakovich,
Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Bayxonov Bahodirjon Tursunbayevich
Doctor of Science (DSc), Professor

Shomurodov Ravshan Tursunkulovich,
PhD, Associate Professor

Boymuratov Abduraxmat Djumayevich
Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics

Sharopova Nafosat Radjabovna
DSc, Associate Professor

Sultanova Kamila Mukhtorali Kizi
Master of Science

CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR IMPLEMENTING TECHNOLOGICAL AND DIGITAL INNOVATIONS.....	10
Shakirxodjayeva Zuxra Rustamxanovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING INVESTMENT PROCESSES IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	16
Aliyeva Zilola Mamatvalyevna	
CURRENT STATE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE SECTORS IN TASHKENT CITY.....	23
Abdikayumov Bekzod Turdiniyozovich	
GREEN BONDS VS. SUSTAINABILITYLINKED LOANS: WHICH WORKS FOR INDUSTRIAL DECARBONISATION?	29
Ataxanov Umidbek Olimovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬЮ БАНКА.....	34
Маликова Дилрабо Муминовна	
ECONOMETRIC MODELLING OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	42
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
AN INTEGRAL INDEX METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE INVESTMENT POTENTIAL OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES	49
Sayyora Bakhtiyorovna Nazirova	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЕ, ПУБЛИЧНЫЕ И ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ: ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ГРАНИЦЫ И ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ.....	53
Срождиддинова Зарина Хайриддиновна	
BLOCKCHAIN-BASED FINANCIAL TRANSACTION MONITORING SYSTEM (SMART CONTRACTS, DECENTRALIZED DATABASE, AND AUDIT TRAILS).....	58
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A DRIVER OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: REGIONAL DISPARITIES AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	65
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN STATISTICAL INDICATORS OF LABOR RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN SURXONDARYO REGION.....	72
Haydarova Dinora Atamurot qizi	
ASSESSING THE ROLE OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH ACROSS THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN USING INTENSITY COEFFICIENTS AND CLUSTER ANALYSIS.....	77
Anvarkhonov Abdulatifkhon Jamshidkhon ugli	
TECHNICAL, ECONOMIC, AND ENVIRONMENTAL EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING AGRIVOLTAIC SYSTEMS IN UZBEKISTAN	85
Jabborov Shaymurod Akram o'g'li	
Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li	
Atoyeva Mohinur Amrilloevna	
Avazov Jonibek Azizbek o'g'li	
МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА НА ТРАЕКТОРИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	91
Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна	
FINANCING GREEN PROJECTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: STATUS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS	97

Qorriyeva Shahnoza Safarbayevna

FORMULA-BASED DISTRIBUTION OF INTERGOVERNMENTAL TRANSFERS TO LOCAL BUDGETS IN UZBEKISTAN: A COMPARATIVE SIMULATION ANALYSIS BASED ON 2026 FORECAST INDICATORS.....	103
Umidjon Pardaev	
Sarvar Maxmudov	
GOVERNMENT FUNDING AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES: FINANCIAL PROMOTION MECHANISMS.....	115
Bahriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
FORECASTING EXPORT AND IMPORT INDICATORS OF BUKHARA REGION	122
Ergashev Mirjon Yorqin o'g'li	
A CUSTOMER-ORIENTED INTEGRATIVE METHODOLOGICAL MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST SERVICES IN THE TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY	130
Bakayev Ziyovuddinkhan Toshbolta ogli	
A PESTLI ANALYSIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM.....	139
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT STATUS AND EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN	146
Khikmatullayeva Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi	
CHANGE MANAGEMENT DURING QUALITY ASSURANCE REFORM IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	154
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
СТРАТЕГИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПАЛОМНИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	162
Каримова Дилафруз Садриддин кизи	
E-COMMERCE AS A DIGITAL FORM OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INCREASING HOUSEHOLD INCOMES.....	167
Eshbayeva Shahnoza Fakhriddinovna	
ADVANTAGES OF IMPLEMENTING AN OCCUPATIONAL AND SKILLS MAPPING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN'S LABOUR MARKET	172
S.B.Goyipnazarov	
S.M.Kurbanbaeva	
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF FIXED ASSETS UTILIZATION IN RAILWAY ENTERPRISES: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN.....	178
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO ASSESSING RESOURCE USE IN THE CONTEXT OF A GREEN ECONOMY.....	183
Karimov Islombek Bekpolat o'g'li	
THE IMPACT OF ECOTOURISM ON REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT	
Samiev Siroj Saitovich	
Ochilova Guli Rashid kizi	
THE IMPACT OF RISK ALLOCATION ON INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (PPP) PROJECTS	197
Khaydarova Charos Nizomiddinovna	
PROSPECTS FOR CHANGING THE VOLUME OF GRAPE CULTIVATION DUE TO THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE VITICULTURE COMPLEX.....	202
Boltaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ	

И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ.....	209
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
ENHANCING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT INFLOWS IN THE POST-CRISIS ERA: AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	215
Foziljon Rustamov Hazratkulovich	
CURRENT STATE AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	219
Musayeva Shoirazimovna	
THE PECULIARITIES OF USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL AREAS.....	225
Makhliso Umarova	
CHALLENGES OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN HUMAN CAPITAL AND STRATEGIES FOR THEIR RESOLUTION.....	231
Aloviddin Zayniddinov Zayniddin ugli	
ANALYSIS OF THE EXPERIENCE OF SUCCESSFUL AGROTOURISM DESTINATIONS IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES: RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UZBEKISTAN.....	237
Aktamov Olimjon Abdugani o'g'li	
ASSESSING THE EFFICIENCY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES EXPORT AT THE REGIONAL LEVEL.....	247
Alimova Shamsiya Abidovna	
ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF BUSINESS ENTITIES AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE FACTORS SHAPING IT: THE CASE OF BUKHARA REGION.....	254
Djurayeva Munira Sadillovovna	
THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE ECONOMY OF BUKHARA REGION AND THEIR DEVELOPMENT TRENDS: AN ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES AND REGIONAL CONCENTRATION.....	261
Azizjon Anvarovich Kadirov	
Nigina Djurayevna Yusupova	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF BORDER TRANSPORT SYSTEMS.....	268
Ikromov Elyor Ibdulloevich	
ПУТИ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ АУДИТОРСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	273
Бобонарова Камола	
GREEN BONDS AND SOVEREIGN DEBT INSTRUMENTS FOR INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET RENEWAL: AN ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL MECHANISMS.....	278
Suleimanov Farrukh	
ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL EXPERIENCES.....	286
Qudratova Gulzoda Mahmudovna	
THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY.....	291
Munisa Abdurakhmonova	
ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH BASED ON THE COBBDOUGLAS PRODUCTION FUNCTION: A CASE STUDY OF SURXONDARYA REGION.....	296
Turaev Bakhtiyor Ergashevich	
GENERAL APPROACHES TO COST REDUCTION IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	302
Kamola Saidova	

GENERAL APPROACHES TO COST REDUCTION IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY

Kamola Saidova
Independent Researcher,
Tashkent Institute of Textile and Light Industry,
Tel.: +998 94 694 10 41

Abstract. This article discusses cost-related issues in the textile industry. Special attention is paid to the classification of costs in industrial enterprises according to various criteria. The article also develops suggestions and recommendations aimed at reducing costs and improving efficiency in the textile industry.

Keywords: textile industry, costs, cost management, cost reduction, economic efficiency.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы затрат в текстильной промышленности. Особое внимание уделено классификации затрат на промышленных предприятиях по различным признакам. Также разработаны предложения и рекомендации, направленные на снижение затрат и повышение эффективности деятельности предприятий текстильной отрасли.

Ключевые слова: текстильная промышленность, затраты, управление затратами, снижение затрат, экономическая эффективность.

INTRODUCTION

In the context of the rational use of natural and industrial resources and the growing global demand for textile products, special attention is being paid to reducing production costs. Considering the socio-economic importance of the industry, it should be noted that “in 2023, the countries that exported the largest volume of textile products in the world included China (USD 154.1 billion), the European Union (USD 64 billion), India (USD 15 billion), Turkey (USD 11.7 billion), the United States (USD 11.4 billion), Vietnam (USD 10 billion), South Korea (USD 7.7 billion), Pakistan (USD 7.1 billion), Taiwan (USD 7 billion), and Japan (USD 5.6 billion)” [1].

Today, in order to increase the competitiveness of textile enterprises in the global market, it is important to organise the production process rationally, further deepen its innovative foundations, improve effective marketing and logistics systems, and reduce production costs.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The legal basis for reducing costs in the textile industry is determined by a number of regulatory and legal documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan. These include the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 28, 2022, No. PF-60¹ “On the Development Strategy of New Uzbekistan for 2022–2026”, the Decree dated May 5, 2020, No. PF-5989² “On Urgent Measures to Support the Textile, Garment and Knitwear Industry”, the Decree dated January 21, 2022, No. PF-53³ “On Measures to Stimulate Deep Processing, Production of High-Value-Added Finished Products and Their Export at Textile, Garment and Knitwear Enterprises”, the Resolution dated February 12, 2019, No. PQ-4186⁴ “On Measures to Further Deepen the Reform of the Textile, Garment and Knitwear Industry and Expand Its Export Potential”, as well as other regulatory documents related to the development of the industry.

The nature and classification of production costs at industrial enterprises, the influence of various factors on them, and their structural and analytical improvement have been studied by a number of foreign and domestic scholars. In particular, the foreign economist G. Fandel examined the foundations of production cost formation at enterprises, the classification of internal and external factors affecting costs, and methods for their identification and assessment [2].

S. Gorodkova considered issues such as the organisational and methodological foundations of effective production cost management, trends in socio-economic cost changes in accordance with market requirements, and innovative approaches to cost management [3].

1 <https://lex.uz/ru/docs/-5841063>

2 <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-4805518>

3 <https://lex.uz/docs/-5833998>

4 <https://lex.uz/uz/docs/-4199421>

Issues related to production cost management at industrial enterprises, improvement of the methodology for accounting and analysing income and expenses, cost accounting and product costing, as well as improving the organisation of cost management, are reflected in the works of Sh. Kudbiyev. The main directions for increasing the economic potential of textile industry enterprises and improving the competitiveness management system are discussed in the works of M. Khudoykulov [4, 5].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research process employed methods such as systematic and economic analysis, induction and deduction, comprehensive assessment, grouping, statistical analysis, and expert evaluation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

In the process of building a New Uzbekistan, large-scale reforms are being implemented to develop a competitive textile industry, produce products that meet global market demand, and establish a complete value-added production chain. Among the priority tasks are the deep processing of yarn through the establishment of a full processing cycle by 2026, the development of projects aimed at eliminating existing gaps in the production chain, the promotion of national brands of finished textile products, and the expansion of their export potential. In particular, it is planned to increase the export volume of finished products under national and foreign brands to USD 5 billion by 2026.

The successful implementation of these objectives requires further expansion of research on effective approaches to reducing production costs at textile enterprises, the development of scientifically grounded cost-reduction strategies, and the formulation of forecast indicators for improving production efficiency.

The influence of economic factors on the classification of production costs and the formation of mechanisms for their reduction was examined. Based on an analysis of current trends in the development of the global textile industry, a framework was proposed that can serve as a methodological basis for the sustainable development and enhanced competitiveness of the domestic textile industry (Table 1).

Table 1
Classification of enterprise expenses⁵

	Classification marks	Types of expenses
1.	By economic sign	-material; -labor; -money.
2.	By participation in business processes	-production costs; -commercial costs; -non-production costs.
3.	By decision-making process	-alternative; -implicit costs.
4.	By types of resources consumed	-material (material); -labor costs; -depreciation; -other costs.
5.	By cost items	-raw materials and supplies; -returnable waste (deducted); - manufactured products, semi-finished products and services purchased from third-party organizations; -fuel and energy costs for technical purposes; -salaries of employees in the main production process; -allocations to extra-budgetary organizations; -costs of preparation and development of production; -general production costs; -general economic costs; -costs of losses due to unusable products; -other production costs; -commercial costs.

⁵ author's development

6.	By dependence on production volume (level of realization)	-constant; -variable.
7.	By the method of distribution between product types	-straight; -curved.
8.	By connection with technological processes	-main; -additional.
9.	By level of regulation	-normative; -non-normative.
10.	By dependence on the direction of enterprise activity	-investment

In this regard, an effective cost management system can be considered as another promising direction for reducing production costs.

Effective cost management involves the establishment of a management support system at the enterprise that enables the adoption of well-grounded managerial decisions based on the use of modern methods of planning, standardisation, budgeting, accounting, and cost analysis.

The central role in addressing this issue is associated with the development of a scientifically grounded system for managing the costs of production and product sales, as well as determining the conditions for its effective application. The existence of an integrated cost management system (ICMS) is a prerequisite for improving the efficiency of production activities. Such a system continuously ensures coordinated actions aimed at the rational use of material, labour, financial, and other resources (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structure of areas provided by the integrated cost management system⁶

Overall, the global textile industry has demonstrated steady growth over the past five years. Despite a number of factors that have negatively affected the development of the industry, its average annual growth rate has remained at approximately 4.1% (Table 2).

**Table 2
Dynamics of development of the global textile industry⁷**

Year	Global textile market value, billions of dollars	Growth rate, %
2018	667.5	1.1%
2019	714.0	7.0%
2020	746.1	4.5%
2021	778.2	4.3%
2022	810.4	4.1%
2023	842.6	4.0%

⁶ author's development
⁷ author's development

The major costs in the textile industry are material costs, primarily those associated with the production or procurement of fibres. After many years of steady growth, global fibre production was significantly affected by the COVID-19 pandemic. As a result, worldwide fibre production declined from 111 million tonnes in 2019 to 109 million tonnes in 2020. However, this reduction was relatively modest compared with the substantial contraction observed in the global apparel retail market.

This situation can largely be explained by the fact that the cotton harvesting and processing season was already underway when the pandemic began. In addition, lower demand in the apparel sector was partially offset by increased demand in other segments, particularly in the medical and hygiene product industries.

Textile enterprises possess considerable potential for reducing production costs. The specific stages and measures implemented in this process should be determined by each enterprise in accordance with the characteristics of its financial, economic, and resource management system.

The global recycled textile market is expected to continue expanding, largely because products manufactured from recycled materials are generally less expensive than those produced from primary raw materials. Nevertheless, the growth of this market may be constrained by several factors, including the insufficient availability of recycling technologies, a shortage of qualified personnel capable of operating such technologies, and a relatively low level of environmental awareness among producers and consumers in certain regions. Despite these challenges, ongoing advancements in recycling technologies are expected to create significant growth opportunities for the recycled textile industry.

Today, one of the most important approaches to reducing production costs in the global textile industry is the implementation of product-sharing practices and the expansion of textile recycling systems (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Classification of ways to reuse and recycle textile products⁸

As a result of the conducted scientific research and the implementation of a production cost reduction system aimed at increasing competitiveness, textile enterprises can achieve higher economic efficiency.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the above considerations, it can be concluded that the legal, economic, and organisational aspects of regulating and stimulating the development of the textile industry have been analysed through the study of the scientific works of classical and modern economists. The cost reduction approaches proposed by the author should be introduced into the activities of textile enterprises in Uzbekistan as important sources of reducing production costs.

In this regard, the organisational structure of cost reduction activities and the importance of each component in improving the efficiency of textile enterprises have been substantiated. The implementation of

⁸ author's development

these measures will contribute to strengthening cost management, increasing competitiveness, and improving the overall economic efficiency of textile enterprises.

REFERENCES

1. Shenglu Fashion. WTO Reports World Textiles and Apparel Trade in 2023 [Electronic resource]. – Available at: <https://shenglufashion.com/2021/08/04/wto-reports-world-textiles-and-apparel-trade-in-2023> (accessed: 10.06.2026).
2. Fandel, G. Theory of Production and Cost. – Berlin; Heidelberg: Springer, 1991. – 378 p. – ISBN 978-3-642-76814-9.
3. Городкова, С. А. Управление затратами субъектов хозяйствования: состояние и трансформация системы: учебное пособие. – Чита: РИК ЗабГУ, 2012. – 215 с.
4. Kudbiev, Sh. Calculation of Production Costs and Its Improvement (on the Example of Enterprises Specializing in Spinning Yarn): Dissertation of Candidate of Economic Sciences. – Tashkent, 2006. – 156 p.
5. Khudoykulov, M. R. Improving the Efficiency of the Management Mechanism in Joint-Stock Companies of the Textile Industry: Dissertation for the Degree of Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics. – Tashkent, 2018. – 142 p.

Proofreader: Xondamir Ismoilov
Layout and Designer: Hasan Maqsudov

2026. № 6

© When materials are reproduced, the ECONOSCITECH-INTEGRATION journal must be cited as the source. Authors are responsible for the accuracy of the information in materials and advertisements published in the journal. Editorial opinions may not always align with those of the authors. Submitted materials will not be returned to the editorial office.

To publish articles in this journal, you may submit articles, advertisements, stories, and other creative materials through the following links. Materials and advertisements are published on a paid basis.

You may subscribe to the journal at any time using the following details. Once subscribed, please send a screenshot or photo of your payment confirmation to our Telegram page @iqtisodiyot_77. Based on this, we will send the latest issue of the journal to your address each month.

Our address: Tashkent city, Yunusobod district, 19th block, House 17.

